

ENDOLYMPHATIC THERAPY FOR ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE APPENDICITIS

A.M. Ashurmetov¹, D.F. Anvarova²

Associate Professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Department of General Surgery and
Fundamentals of Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15459188>

Abstract. *Complicated inflammatory and destructive diseases of acute appendicitis and abdominal organs represent one of the most challenging sections of modern surgery. Due to diagnostic difficulties, these conditions often lead to numerous complications and increased mortality rates, underlining the urgency of scientific research in this field (Panchenkov R.T., 1990; Skripnichenko D.F., 1986). The therapeutic effect of endolymphatic drug therapy is based on several mechanisms: ensuring high concentrations of the drugs in the lymph nodes and the site of inflammation, cooperation of lymph node lymphocytes, normalization of the microcirculation system, and immunomodulation in lymph nodes at the microvessel and interstitial levels. A medical examination was conducted on 36 patients with acute inflammatory pathology of the abdominal cavity—destructive appendicitis—who were treated in the surgical departments of clinics in Tashkent.*

Keywords: *lymphatic system, direct endolymphatic therapy (DET), peritonitis, surgical infections, endolymphatic antibiotic therapy (ELAT).*

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, the prevention and treatment of various infections that lead to acute surgical inflammatory diseases, as well as numerous postoperative complications—including surgical sepsis and septic shock—have become a priority direction in medicine (Savelyev V.S., 2019, 2020). This drives the need to identify effective methods for administering antibacterial and other therapeutic agents.

The decreasing effectiveness of antibacterial therapy in recent years is due to several factors, including the rapid emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains of microorganisms, an increase in surgical inflammatory diseases, a growing volume of surgical interventions in critically ill patients, irrational use of antibiotics, and difficulties in creating adequate treatment methods. In particular, insufficient drug concentration at the pathological site is a key issue (Loxvitskiy S.V., et al., 1992). Developing rational approaches to antibacterial therapy stimulates the creation of pathogenetically justified methods, especially critical in treating purulent-septic complications arising from prolonged antibiotic therapy (Golbraikh V.A., 1998).

Recently, the direct administration of drugs via the endolymphatic route by catheterizing peripheral lymphatic vessels has been developed and applied. Incorporating direct endolymphatic antibiotic therapy (DET) into the treatment protocols for acute abdominal pathology significantly enhances therapeutic outcomes. This method reduces the course doses of antibiotics, decreases the incidence of purulent-septic complications, and, most importantly, accelerates patient recovery (Yarema I.V., et al., 1993, 2008; Virenkov Yu.E., et al., 1987; Ashurmetov A.M., 1996, 1998, 2002, 2020, 2021).

However, many aspects of studying the body's responses to DET and treating pathological processes that directly affect the lymphatic system remain insufficiently researched. This

highlights the need for further scientific investigation in this area (V.I. Vtorenko, et al., 2008). The literature provides insufficient coverage of criteria for DET indications and contraindications, the daily and course volumes of fluids administered, and the timing and duration of endolymphatic therapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The study analyzed 36 patients with appendicular peritonitis who were treated in the surgical departments of clinics in Tashkent. All patients were divided into two groups. The first group (main group) included endolymphatic therapy in the treatment protocol. The second group (control group) did not receive lymphogenic treatment methods. All patients underwent dynamic laboratory examinations of biological media (blood, urine, lymph). Biochemical analysis measured total protein and its fractions, residual nitrogen, creatinine, cholesterol, diastase, and other parameters. Immunological indices and toxicity markers (LII, NDI), as well as clinical indicators (SAPS-II, APACHE-II), were determined. Patients in the first group underwent catheterization of peripheral lymphatic vessels in the lower third of the leg or in the region of the Lisfranc joint following a standard technique developed by the department in 1982. The second group (control group) comprised 20 patients who did not receive lymphogenic therapy. Patients with peritonitis as a complication of acute appendicitis were selected for observation. All patients underwent dynamic laboratory examinations of biological media (blood, urine, lymph). Biochemical analyses determined levels of total protein and its fractions, urea, creatinine, cholesterol, diastase, and blood sugar.

In patients with severe intoxication, drainage of the thoracic lymphatic duct (TLD) was performed in five cases following the department's standard technique (1989). Depending on the indications, antibiotics, proteolytic enzyme inhibitors, heparin, and rheological preparations were administered into the catheterized peripheral lymphatic vessels. The combination, dosages, and volumes of the drugs were adjusted based on the severity and origin of peritonitis and the patient's condition. Immunological tests were conducted on the 14th day of treatment, assessing key parameters, including the absolute and relative count of total T-lymphocytes, their subpopulations, and phagocytic activity using the Zemskov method. Basic biochemical parameters were analyzed using Kamyshnikov's methodology.

Statistical processing was performed using the STATISTICA software package (version 11 for Windows). Statistical reliability was assessed using non-parametric criteria such as the Wilcoxon test for paired comparisons and the Mann-Whitney U-test for comparing groups based on a single parameter. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The lymphatic system plays a crucial role in the development of destructive changes at the site of inflammation. The sequence of reactions leading to edema at the inflammatory site is associated with increased exudation from blood vessels and slowed reabsorption of fluid and colloid substances from the intercellular spaces by the lymphatic system. The developing edema significantly hinders tissue trophism at the inflammatory site, resulting in the accumulation of under-oxidized metabolic products and cellular necrosis, which in turn increases the body's toxin reservoir. The chosen endolymphatic drugs were based on these conditions. For example, using only antibiotics might not always guarantee their penetration into the inflammatory and regional lymph nodes. However, following lymphatic heparinization, the likelihood of targeted antibiotic delivery significantly increases.

We, like other researchers, noted that endolymphatic infusions accelerate the movement of lymph through the main lymphatic vessels. This phenomenon was also observed in clinical observations of patients with endotoxemia, where toxic lymph flowed intensely into the

bloodstream. Usually, a few hours after endolymphatic antibiotic infusion, patients experienced a temporary rise in body temperature and exacerbation of intoxication symptoms, which was associated with this lymphatic drainage.

In addition to their barrier and detoxification functions, lymph nodes play an active role in immunological protection. All subpopulations of lymphocytes are preserved and proliferate within them. Therefore, eliminating microorganisms and their toxins in the lymph nodes as an etiological factor of degenerative changes naturally helps restore the body's immunological reactivity. However, in some cases, particularly with severe lymphopenia, immunogenesis stimulation is necessary. For such cases, endolymphatic administration of T-activin was prescribed after the acute inflammation subsided.

Endolymphatic therapy was conducted against the background of generally accepted treatment methods aimed at correcting water-electrolyte, protein, and vitamin metabolism, normalizing the acid-base balance, and preventing potential complications in vital organs and systems. At the same time, the administration of antibiotics, heparin, anti-enzyme agents, and T-activin was performed exclusively through the endolymphatic route as per indications.

The quantitative composition of prescribed drugs, the volumes of infused solutions, the sequence of endolymphatic infusions, and the timing of therapy were determined based on the characteristics of the disease's course in patients. In general, all patients in the main group could be divided into two subgroups:

1. Those with localized peritonitis.
2. Those with diffuse peritonitis.

Patients in the second subgroup typically arrived at the clinic with complications that developed during the postoperative period after undergoing antibiotic therapy and surgical interventions using suboptimal methods. For patients in the first subgroup, endolymphatic therapy began in the early postoperative period, sometimes even before surgical treatment. In the second subgroup, therapy commenced 4–6 days or more after the onset of the disease. For these subgroups, DET tactics included antibiotic therapy, administration of proteolytic enzyme inhibitors, correction of microcirculatory disorders, and detoxification therapy as needed.

For widespread forms of peritonitis, the DET tactic differed in that endolymphatic antibiotic therapy was initiated alongside conventional antibiotic administration. If no positive effects were observed within 3–4 days (e.g., normalization of temperature, reduction in leukocytosis, and resumption of intestinal peristalsis), the drugs were replaced.

Treatment results. After catheterizing the peripheral lymphatic vessels, 2.0 ml of heparin (2,500 IU) dissolved in saline was administered (0.5–0.6 ml per minute). Broad-spectrum antibiotics, such as cephalosporins and aminoglycosides, were predominantly used. Cephalosporins were administered at a dose of 1.0 g once daily (III–IV generation), while gentamicin was given at 80 mg once daily in a volume of 2 ml. In some patients with severe intoxication syndrome, the regimen was supplemented with the endolymphatic infusion of 15–20 ml of Reosorbilact, administered 6–8 hours after antibiotics or protease inhibitors to prevent drug interaction. Infusion was performed slowly over 25–30 minutes, with 3–4 infusions conducted during the treatment course. If lymphopenia fell below 17%, T-activin was administered endolymphatically 1–1.5 hours after antibiotics at a dose of 100 mg, 3 times over 1–2 days.

The immunological indicators in patients with peritonitis were analyzed on the 14th day of treatment. The findings are summarized in the table below:

Indicator (measurement unit)	Normal Values (n=36)	Comparative Groups	Main Group (Day 14 of Treatment)	Control Group (Day 14 of Treatment)
Total T-lymphocytes (E-ROK), abs.x10 ⁹ /l	1.15±0.2	0.63±0.1	0.89±0.09	0.67±0.1
T-helpers, abs.x10 ⁹ /l	0.72±0.04	0.42±0.07	0.63±0.06	0.47±0.09
T-suppressors, abs.x10 ⁹ /l	0.52±0.03	0.36±0.02	0.41±0.09	0.49±0.05
B-lymphocytes (M-ROK), abs.x10 ⁹ /l	0.15±0.03	0.11±0.02	0.18±0.03	0.12±0.02
IgG (g/l)	11.3±0.6	12.4±0.3	21.6±1.1	8.4±0.2
IgA (g/l)	1.9±0.07	2.3±0.04	2.1±0.04	0.9±0.03
IgM (g/l)	1.2±0.03	0.9±0.03	1.1±0.03	0.7±0.02
Neutrophil phagocytic activity (%)	60.2±2.7	41.7±2.56	69.9±4.3	46.4±2.7

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In patients with peritonitis, the initial absolute count of total T-lymphocytes (E-ROK) in both groups was significantly lower than normal, being reduced by 1.83 times in the main group and 1.79 times in the control group. There was no significant difference between the two groups initially ($z=0.39$; $p=0.69$).

On the 14th day of treatment, the main group showed a 1.41-fold increase in T-lymphocyte counts, while the control group only exhibited a 4.5% rise ($z=3.06$; $p=0.0022$). Compared to normal values, T-lymphocyte levels in the main group decreased by 22.6%, while in the control group, the reduction reached 41.7%. Similar trends were observed for T-helper cells. On the 14th day, the main group exhibited a 1.5-fold increase in T-helper counts, whereas the control group showed only a 12.8% rise. The reduction in T-helper levels in the main group was -12.5% compared to normal values, while in the control group, the reduction was significantly higher at -34.7%. Regarding T-suppressor cells, there was no significant difference between the groups on the 14th day. However, the increase in T-suppressor counts in the control group (+24.5%) might indirectly indicate ongoing destruction and the development of purulent-septic complications. Analysis of humoral immunity parameters revealed a 30.9% increase in B-lymphocyte counts in the main group, compared to only 8.3% in the control group. This suggests enhanced differentiation and activation of antigen-presenting cells in the main group. The IgG levels in the

main group increased by 1.7 times on the 14th day, while in the control group, IgG levels decreased by 1.35 times compared to normal values. A significant difference in IgG levels was observed between the two groups ($z=2.35$; $p=0.018$).

In the comparative groups, the initial IgA levels exceeded the normal values by 1.21 times in the main group and by 1.22 times in the control group, possibly due to the activation of B-lymphocyte zones presenting antigens in the gastrointestinal mucosa.

By the 14th day of treatment, IgA levels in the main group nearly returned to normal, while in the control group, IgA levels fell to 2.1 times below the norm ($z=2.5$; $p=0.013$). The initial IgM levels in the comparative groups were reduced by 1.33 times and 1.34 times, respectively ($p=0.64$). By the 14th day, IgM levels in the main group increased by 1.55 times, slightly exceeding the normal values.

In contrast, IgM levels in the control group continued to decrease by 1.27 times from their initial values, remaining 41.7% below the norm. An analysis of treatment outcomes on the 14th day revealed a two-fold difference in IgM levels between the groups ($z=3.56$; $p=0.0037$).

Regarding phagocytic activity, the initial neutrophil phagocytic activity in both groups was identical ($z=0.09$; $p=0.93$), amounting to -30.4% of normal values. By the 14th day of treatment, neutrophil phagocytic activity in the main group had increased by 1.68 times, while in the control group, the increase was only 9.7%, reaching -22.9% of normal values.

CONCLUSION. 1. Direct endolymphatic therapy (DET) in patients with appendicular peritonitis achieves effects of anticoagulation, antibacterial action, detoxification, and immunostimulation.

2. DET increases the absolute counts of total T-lymphocytes and T-helper cells, enhances the levels of IgG and IgM immunoglobulins, and activates the phagocytic activity of immune cells.

3. Endolymphatic infusions accelerate lymphatic transport through the lymphatic system and its entry into the bloodstream, leading to the normalization of the microcirculation system.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуразакова Д. А. и др. Efficiency of endolymphatic drug administration //Молодойученый. – 2018. – №. 9. – С. 61-62.
2. Агзамова М. Н. и др. Изучение микробной флоры при перитонитах //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 1. – С. 33-34.
3. Агзамова М. Н., Зупаров К. Ф., Зикрилла Т. З. Окислительный статус во время аллопластики у больных с послеоперационной вентральной грыжей //Инфекция, иммунитет и фармакология. – 1999. – С. 5.
4. Ахмедов М. Д. и др. Цитохромоксидазнаяактивность печёночной паренхимы при различных сроках ишемии и обтурационнойжелтухе //European science. – 2019. – №. 2 (44). – С. 71-75.
5. Ашурметов А. М. и др. Лимфоиммунностимуляция при разлитом гнойном перитоните //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 7. – С. 103-105.
6. Жафаров Х. М. и др. Способ лечения гнойно-воспалительных заболеваний у больных сахарным диабетом //Паллиативная медицина и реабилитация. – 2002. – №. 2-3. – С. 113.
7. Исмаилов Ф. М. и др. Causes of death in emergency conditions of the abdominal organs //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 8. – С. 44-46.

8. Наврузов С. Н., Мехмонов Ш. Р., Долимов К. С. Расширенные и комбинированные операции при толстокишечной непроходимости //Бюллетень ассоциации врачей Узбекистана. – 2003. – Т. 3. – С. 20-23.
9. Abdumajidov A. Et al. COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PYO-INFLAMMATORY DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2019. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 57-59.
10. Akhmedov A. I., Tursumetov A. A., Zhafarov K. M. Features of allohernioplasty for postoperative ventral hernias in the on-lay position under conditions of infection in the experiment //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 3. – С. 3897-3905.
11. Buyanov V.M., Rodoman G.V., Laberko L.A. Diffuz peritonitda endogen intoksikatsiyani baholashning zamonaviy usullari // I Moskvaxalqaro jarrohlar kongressi. Hisobotlarning tezislari. M/, 1995 yil. Bilan. 16–17.
12. Ermolov A.S., Udovskiy E.E., Grigoryan A.R. Jarrohlik infeksiyasining endolimfatik antibiotik terapiyasida nospesifik gumoral immunitet holati. Xirurgiya. 1987 yil. № 1. S. 76–79.
13. Golbraikh V.A.. Qorin bo'shlig'i organlarining yiringli-yallig'lanish kasalliklari bilan og'rigan bemorlarni kompleks davolashda endolimfatik terapiya. Abstrakt Dis. Dok. Asal. Fanlar. M., 1998. 34 b.
14. Jafarov K., Melnik I. Immediate Results of Surgical Treatment of Patients with Strangulated of Ventral Hernia of the Anterior Abdominal Wall //Asian Pacific Journal of Environment and Cancer. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. S1. – С. 13-14.
15. Mirzakhidovich J. K., Abdumalikovich T. A., Ibrogimovich A. A. Prevention of Postoperative Wound Complications in Rappeded Abdominal Hernia //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 6473–6484-6473–6484.